

Synthesis of the 1,3,5-Trimethylcyclohexanes via a Wittig Reaction

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A new synthetic route was devised for the preparation of the geometric isomers of the 1,3,5-trimethylcyclohexanes. Xylenol was hydrogenated to give a mixture of alcohols which were oxidized to their corresponding ketones. A Wittig reaction involving triphenylphosphinemethylene hydrobromide and the ketones produced the corresponding exomethylenecyclohexanes which were hydrogenated to the saturated hydrocarbons.

In continuation of our study¹ of the synthesis of the hydrocarbons found in petroleum, a new synthetic route was devised for the preparation of the two geometric isomers of the 1, 3, 5-trimethylcyclohexanes.

The possibilities of the Wittig reaction between phosphoranes (phosphonium salts plus base) and aldehydes or ketones have evoked considerable interest as a convenient route towards the synthesis of a variety of olefins^{2,3,4}.

The present work describes the preparation of the two isomeric *cis* and *trans*-3,5-dimethylmethylenecyclohexanes from the corresponding xylenol and their further hydrogenation to the 1,3,5-isomeric trimethylcyclohexanes without conformational implications.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hydrogenation of 3,5-xylenol over Harshaw nickel afforded a mixture of *ccc*, *cc* and *ctc*-dimethylcyclohexanols which on fractional distillation, separated out only the *ccc* alcohol as a solid while the other two alcohols remained as a mixture that could only be separated out by preparative gas liquid chromatography. Their physical properties are given in Table I and are in agreement with the literature⁵.

TABLE I

(3) CH ₃	(5) CH ₃	(1) OH	M.P.	B.P./17mm	n _D ²⁰	d ₄ ²⁰
<i>cis</i>	<i>cis</i>	<i>cis</i>	39-40°	79-80°	1.4519	.894
<i>cis</i>	<i>cis</i>	<i>trans</i>	16°	83-84°	1.4556	.899
<i>cis</i>	<i>trans</i>	<i>cis</i>	liquid	84°	1.4584	.906

1. B. H. Mahmoud and K. W. Greenlee, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **27**, 2369.

2. G. Wittig and G. Geissler, *Ann.*, 1953, **580**, 44.

3. G. Wittig and Schollkopf, *Ber.*, 1954, **87**, 1318.

4. Tippet, 'The Wittig Reaction', in "Advances in Organic Chemistry: Methods and Results" Vol. 1 ed. Interscience, New York, 1960.

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Oxidation⁶ of the solid *ccc* alcohol gave the corresponding ketone in a high yield and in 99% purity as determined by gas chromatography. Oxidation of a 35: 65 mixture of the *ctc* : *cct* alcohols gave mixture of *trans* and *cis* dimethylketones in the same ratio. A small pure sample of the *cct* alcohol obtained by gas chromatography gave on oxidation a ketone identical to that obtained from the *ccc* alcohol due to the *cis* relationship of the two methyl groups in both the *ccc* and *cct* alcohols.

A Wittig reaction with triphenylphosphinemethylene hydrobromide and sodium amide in *glyme* with the pure *cis* ketone gave the corresponding *cis*, dimethylmethylene-cyclohexane while reaction with a mixture of *cis* and *trans* ketones gave a corresponding mixture of *cis* and *trans* ketones gave a corresponding mixture of *cis* and *trans* olefins, Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

Hydrogenation of the individual exomethylenecyclohexanes afforded the corresponding trimethylcyclohexanes that were fractionated apart by gas chromatography and identified.

EXPERIMENTAL*

cis- and *trans*-3,5-Dimethylcyclohexanols :

Xylenol was hydrogenated over Harshaw nickel in an autoclave and the resulting mixture of *ccc*, *cct* and *ctc*-3,5-dimethylcyclohexanols, 450 g (3.5 moles) was distilled on a column at 20-plate efficiency. The all *cis* alcohol 145 g. (1.1 moles), b.p. 177.5-178°, n_D^{20} 1.4509-1.4515, m.p. 39°, distilled over first and the rest of the material was fractionated under vacuum, b.p. 83-85°/17 mm., n_D^{20} 1.540-1.4572 with no definite flat in the distillation. The all *cis* alcohol was recrystallized from ethanol 5 times to give a white solid, m.p. 40-40.3°. The end fraction of the distillate, 100 g., composed of the *ctc* and *cct* isomers were combined and chilled in the refrigerator overnight. A small amount of the solid that formed, 16 g was filtered off and the filtrate was distilled on a Nestor-Faust spinning band under vacuum, b.p. 84-85°/17 mm., n_D^{20} 1.4557-1.4570. G.L.C. analysis showed that all fractions were mixtures of two components ranging from ratios of 80:20 to 35:65.

*m.p. s are uncorrected.

6. H. C. Brown and C. P. Gorg., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 2952.

Oxidation of cis-3,5-dimethylcyclohexanol. Ethyl ether, 400 ml and 128 g (1 mole) of *cis*-3,5-dimethylcyclohexanol were placed in a one liter, 3-necked flask fitted with a stirrer, condenser and addition funnel. The chromic acid solution, prepared from 100 g (1 mole) sodium dichromate dihydrate and 75 ml (1.3 moles) of 96% sulphuric acid diluted to 500 ml, was added to the stirred solution over 30 minutes, maintaining the temperature at 25°. After 2 hr, the upper layer was separated and the aqueous phase extracted 3 times with 50-ml portions of ether. The combined extracts were washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate, then water. G.L.C. analysis on a squalane column showed 99% ketone and 1% alcohol. Distillation gave 114.1 g (90.6%) yield of ketone, b.p. 181.1-181.3°, n_D^{20} 1.4423.

Oxidation of a mixture of trans-3, 5-dimethylcyclohexanols : A 35:65, *cis*:*trans* concentrate of the alcohol 70 g (0.5 mole) oxidized under the same conditions as above gave 58.5 g, (93% yield) of ketone, b.p. 82-85°/30 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4428-1.447. G.L.C. analysis showed this to be a mixture of *cis* and *trans* ketones in a 35:65 ratio.

cis-3,5-dimethylmethylenecyclohexane: To an ice cooled solution of triphenyl phosphine, 262 g (1 mole) in 2 liters of benzene, methyl bromide, 105 g (1.1 moles) was added while stirring. A voluminous precipitate developed after 3 hr which was filtered and washed with a little cold petroleum ether and dried in a desiccator under vacuum. A nearly quantitative yield of triphenylphosphinemethylene hydrobromide was obtained.

To a nitrogen filled 3-necked flask fitted with a reflux condenser, stirrer and addition funnel was placed 40 g (0.11 mole) of triphenylphosphinemethylene hydrobromide, 250 ml of sodium dried glyme and 13 g (0.3 mole) of sodium amide. The mixture was heated to reflux for 3 hr at which time the color changed to deep orange. *cis*-3,5-dimethyl cyclohexanone 12.8 g (0.1 mole) in 15 ml of glyme was added very slowly and after the addition, a reflux was maintained for 10 hr. The mixture was cooled and the precipitated triphenylphosphite was filtered off. The filtrate was then distilled to one third its volume, washed 3 times with water and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulfate. Distillation gave 9.2 g (72%) of pure 1, *cis*-3, *cis*-5-dimethylmethylenecyclohexane, b.p. 139.4°. Calc. for C_9H_{16} : C, 87.03; H, 12.97. Found: C, 87.20; H, 12.89.

trans-3,5 dimethylmethylenecyclohexane: The predominantly *trans* ketone mixture (35:65) was similarly subjected to a Wittig reaction to give a 35:65 mixture of *cis* and *trans*-3, 5-dimethylmethylenecyclohexane. The pure *trans* compound was isolated by quantitative G.L.C., b.p. 140.2°, n_D^{20} 1.4267. Calc. for C_9H_{16} : C, 87.03; H, 12.97. Found: C, 87.17; H, 12.95.

1, *cis*-3, *cis*-5-trimethylcyclohexane: 10 ml of *cis*-3,5-dimethylmethylenecyclohexane was hydrogenated to saturation at room temperature over 5% platinum catalyst. The product was saturated to bromine and G.L.C. indicated the presence of two components in a 65:35 ratio. They could not be separated apart by distillation but quantitative G.L.C. separated out enough pure sample for physical determinations. A first component, b.p. 138.5°, n_D^{20} 1.4266, and a second component b.p. 141.2°, n_D^{20} 1.4308. Infrared spectra and G.L.C. retention times showed them to be *ccc* and *cct*-1,3,5-trimethylcyclohexane respectively.

The *trans* olefin concentrate gave on hydrogenation a mixture with a predominance of the *cct* isomer.

1. 30/70 (*cis/trans*) olefins gave 20/80 cycloparaffins (theoretical 19/81)
2. 60/40 (*cis/trans*) olefins gave 37/63 cycloparaffins (theoretical 39/61)

The paraffins were identified by G.L.C. retention times and I.R. spectra.

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